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THE DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' SKILLS FOR CREATIVE ENGINEERING PROJECTS

UDK 37.047

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Abstract: This article develops the concept of a methodological system for fostering SIID (Students' Innovative and Inventive Development) among technical university students during the study of general technical disciplines. It substantiates the necessity and potential of enhancing students' skills for innovative engineering activities in this context. The methodological system for teaching students should be structured based on a block-hierarchical principle and should include motivational-target, content, procedural, technological, and diagnostic components. It also emphasizes the interrelation between natural sciences, general technical, and specialized disciplines.

The development of general technical disciplines in higher education institutions should integrate creative, competency-based, activity-based, modular, and differentiated approaches that contribute to the formation of students' CIID (Creative and Inventive Industrial Development). Furthermore, the principles of fundamental unity and professional orientation in training must be considered, along with individual student characteristics. The methodological system for fostering CIID among technical university students should be based on the integration of the core course "Mechanics" with related academic subjects, as well as student extracurricular activities within the framework of competitions and research initiatives.

Key words: engineering inventiveness, competency, block-hierarchical principle, professional orientation, creative product, broad technical discipline, didactic principle.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada texnik oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining umumiy texnik fanlarni o'qitish jarayonida innovatsion muhandislik faoliyatiga qobiliyatlarini shakllantirish zarurati va imkoniyatlari asoslab berilgan. Shuningdek, tabiiy-ilmiiy, umumiy texnik va maxsus fanlarning o'zaro bog'liqligi kontekstida SIID (talabalarning innovatsion muhandislik faoliyati qobiliyatlari)ni shakllantirishning uslubiy tizimi konsepsiyasi ishlab chiqilgan.

Mazkur uslubiy tizim quyidagi qoidalarni o'z ichiga oladi: ierarxik tamoyilga asoslangan tizimli tuzilish, shuningdek, motivatsion-maqсадli, mazmuniiy, jarayonli-texnologik va diagnostik tarkibiy qismlarni qamrab oladi. Texnik oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarini umumiy texnik fanlarga o'qitishning uslubiy tizimi SIIDni shakllantirishga ko'maklashuvchi innovatsion, kompetensiyaviy, faoliyatga yo'naltirilgan, modulli va tabaqalashtirilgan yondashuvlarni integratsiyalash asosida tashkil etilishi lozim.

Shuningdek, talabalarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda fundamental ta'lim va kasbiy yo'naltirilganlikning uzviyligi tamoyillari ham e'tiborga olinishi kerak. Texnik universitetlar talabalarida SIIDni shakllantirish uslubiy tizimi "Mexanika" asosiy kursini tegishli o'quv fanlari bilan integratsiya qilish, shuningdek, olimpiadalar va ilmiy-tadqiqot faoliyati doirasida talabalar darsdan tashqari ishlarini tashkil etish orqali amalga oshirilishi lozim.

Kalit so'zlar: umumiy texnik fan, blok-ierarxik tamoyil, kasbiy yo'naltirish, innovatsion mahsulot, kompetensiya, didaktik tamoyil, muhandislik ijodkorligi.

Аннотация: В статье разработана концепция методической системы формирования у студентов технических вузов СИИД (Способностей к Инновационной и Инженерной Деятельности) в процессе изучения общетехнических дисциплин. Обоснована необходимость и возможность развития у студентов навыков для инновационной инженерной деятельности. Структура методической системы должна быть сформирована на основе блочно-иерархического принципа и включать мотивационно-целевой, содержательный, процессуально-технологический и диагностический компоненты. Также рассмотрена взаимосвязь естественно-научных, общетехнических и специальных дисциплин.

Развитие общетехнических дисциплин в высших учебных заведениях должно основываться на интеграции креативного, компетентностного, деятельностного, модульного и дифференцированного подходов, способствующих формированию СИИД у студентов. Кроме того, необходимо учитывать принципы единства фундаментальности и профессиональной направленности обучения, а также индивидуальные особенности студентов. Методическая система формирования СИИД у студентов технических вузов должна строиться на основе интеграции курса “Механика” с сопутствующими учебными дисциплинами, а также внеаудиторной работы студентов в условиях олимпиадной и научно-исследовательской деятельности.

Ключевые слова: общетехническая дисциплина, блочно-иерархический принцип, профессиональная направленность, инновационный продукт, компетентность, дидактический принцип, инженерное творчество.

INTRODUCTION

The modern theory of innovation, an understanding of the cyclical patterns of generational change and technological trends, technological structures, and production methods, along with the appropriate institutional frameworks and the strategic application of market economic mechanisms, form the foundation of Uzbekistan’s innovative economic development path.

This approach is implemented through innovation activity, a cyclical process that begins with the development of a potential new product and culminates in its industrial production and market launch. Under these circumstances, training specialists capable of engaging in innovative activities becomes one of the primary objectives of higher professional education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Even though some colleges already train these professionals, the majority of their graduates are managers who research sales marketplaces and advertise products there. Technical and engineering experts who directly create an innovative product (IP) are still largely trained using conventional knowledge and disciplinary approaches, which do not fully address the demands of contemporary, creative businesses [1-3].

Accordingly, the urgent need to train these specialists is emphasized in the following official documents and programs: the State’s 2020 Higher Professional Education Reform Program, the State Target Development Program, the fundamentals of the National Engineering Education Doctrine, the agreements on accession to the Bologna and Copenhagen processes, and the education strategy for the years 2020–2025.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

General technical disciplines play a crucial role in fulfilling the tasks assigned within the higher professional education system, forming the foundation of engineering knowledge for future experts.

Analysis and Results

The capacity to engineer and develop innovative activities (IID) is crucial. Since bachelor’s degree holders will constitute the majority (up to 70%) of all specialists with higher education, general technical disciplines not only retain their significance in the transition to a two-level educational system but also begin to play a pivotal role.

On a much smaller scale, master’s degree holders are specialists with extensive professional knowledge and innovative skills, enabling them to conduct scientific research and solve complex engineering challenges. Additionally, they will be able to autonomously adapt and secure employment in the labor market after receiving broad technical training.

The concept of innovative engineering activity is defined as the process of developing and producing new machinery and technologies (innovative products) that are brought to market as commercial products. These products are represented by technical documentation, industrial designs, or intellectual property protection documents.

This process ensures social, economic, or other impacts while maintaining competitiveness in both domestic and foreign markets. The IID framework has been established, outlining its key attributes, categories of innovative activities and products, and the information they encompass. Figure 1 illustrates the algorithm used to develop an innovative product [4-5].

Figure 1: All-purpose algorithm for acquiring novel goods

An expert must possess specific IID-related skills, which are developed and refined during the learning process, in order to effectively apply IID. This study also formulated a working definition of inventive skills. Engineering activity is understood as a collection of interrelated personal cognitive traits that determine a student's suitability for innovative engineering activities—whether they can develop and succeed under such conditions while possessing the necessary knowledge and abilities, and whether they are prepared to acquire new methods and techniques. The SIID framework, comprising a motivational-need component, a “set of higher mental functions” component, an operational-activity component, and the corresponding skills, was established by N.L. Kurileva based on the generalized structure of technical abilities defined by M.G. Davletshina.

The framework includes: The capacity for creative problem-solving; Possession of fundamental knowledge; Possession of general technical knowledge; The ability to solve engineering problems; Mastery of production technology; The capacity for problem formulation; The capacity for design; The capacity for invention; The capacity for decision-making; Teamwork skills; Multidisciplinary knowledge; The ability to deliver solutions in their final form; The capacity to create and modify mechanical systems [6-7]. The results of an empirical experiment conducted among instructors and students at multiple technical universities across the country are presented. This study enabled an evaluation of the role and significance of academic discipline cycles, as well as various aspects of the comprehensive training system for engineers in shaping students' characteristics related to SID.

Additionally, the study examined the extent to which students apply fundamental and general technical knowledge when addressing professional challenges in an innovative economy. It is assumed that both new approaches to the science of mechanics and contemporary methodological approaches that foster creative potential development, along with pedagogical technologies (e.g., structuring scientific and technical knowledge, innovation, cooperation), should be employed to address the issue of SID development in students during the instruction of general professional disciplines. Additionally, the integration of foundational “Mechanics” coursework, related courses, and extracurricular training within competition and research environments should be utilized. The systems approach (as described by N.M. Anisimov) was most effectively applied in structuring the system, establishing interconnections, evaluating and identifying components, and optimizing the learning environment.

The activity-based approach (developed by B.A. Golub, G.S. Kochetkova, A.Ya. Nain, G.N. Stainov, D.V. Chernilevsky, et al.) was used to define educational tasks, select teaching tools (such as research and project-based activities), determine content, choose material presentation formats, monitor learning outcomes, and establish learning objectives. The competency-based approach (as formulated by I.D. Belonovskaya, I.A. Zimnyaya, Yu.G. Tatur, et al.) enabled the structuring of SIID, identifying the key competencies that characterize a student's ability to solve professional challenges in their future SIID-related activities. The innovative approach to learning (outlined by B.L. Agranovich, N.M. Anisimov, G.V. Belonovskaya, V.M. Zhurakovsky, V.V. Larionov, Yu.P. Pokholkov, V.M. Polonsky, et al.) allowed for the selection of effective methods and tools to facilitate the development of SIID in both the “Mechanics” course and related subjects, as well as within Olympiad and research environments. Several instructional strategies were implemented, including contextual learning, which fosters CIID by linking specific knowledge to its practical applications; experiential learning, which involves integrating students' personal experiences with the subject matter; an interdisciplinary approach, where students independently acquire knowledge from different disciplines and apply it to solve professional engineering problems; and team-based learning, which simulates real-world IED environments, allowing students to gain experience in solving complex engineering challenges while distributing tasks and responsibilities within a team [8-9].

In addition to these approaches, differentiated learning, individualized and professionally-oriented methods, problem-based learning, developmental learning, modular and active learning, and collaborative pedagogy—

alongside elements of complete assimilation pedagogy—were employed in the study to enhance educational engagement. These methods contribute to effective interaction between educators and learners. The effectiveness of preparing students for IID was further supported by a system of didactic principles, which included both special and general principles. Special principles: Integration, as well as the principle of unity between fundamental and professional orientation, implemented in teaching methodologies. General principles: The unity of science and education, polytechnic and professional orientation, systematicity and consistency, interdisciplinary connections, visualization in education, accessibility, individualization and differentiation, conscious and active learning, fostering motivation, and complete knowledge assimilation. These principles guide instructors toward solving the challenges of developing AIDS.

Based on these approaches and provisions, a concept was developed for the formation of CIID among students of technical universities, structured according to the following principles: the methodological system should be formed following a block-hierarchical principle and should include motivational-target, content, procedural-technological, and diagnostic components. The methodological system for training university students in general technical disciplines must be based on the integration of innovative, competence-based, activity-based, modular, and differentiated approaches. These approaches contribute to the formation of students' CIID and uphold the principles of unity between fundamental and professional orientation while considering the individual characteristics of students. The methodological system for developing CIID in technical university students should integrate instruction in the core course “Mechanics” with related academic disciplines, as well as with extracurricular activities conducted in a competitive and research-based environment. The methods, forms, and tools used in the SIID formation system, alongside traditional approaches, should align with the methodological orientation of general technical disciplines toward professional IID. These methods should also reflect the relationship between curricular content and high-tech innovations in modern enterprises that produce innovative products [10-11].

The creative independent work of students in academic competitions and scientific research serves as an educational IID aimed at SIID formation. It should align with contemporary scientific and practical challenges associated with developing innovative products at the level of projects, patents, and manufacturing. Furthermore, it should facilitate interaction between stakeholders in the educational process, including teaching methodologies, learning tools, and the operational management of these processes. The SIID formation model (Figure 2) consists of motivational-goal-oriented, methodological, process-technological, and diagnostic components. The motivational-goal-oriented component includes a hierarchy of objectives, with the primary goal being to enhance the efficiency of training specialists for IID by developing specific competencies. These competencies are defined by subject-specific and interdisciplinary knowledge and by fostering students' intrinsic motivation to develop SIID consciously. Specific objectives include: developing knowledge of machine part calculation algorithms, ensuring optimal operational characteristics of components and assemblies (strength, reliability, durability); establishing experimental knowledge of the physical-mechanical properties of components under various production and operational conditions; creating a database of machine-building components, machinery properties, and application fields; instilling a scientific conviction that the “Mechanics” discipline serves as the fundamental basis for all technological disciplines involved in designing, constructing, manufacturing, and operating machine components; developing creative thinking in engineering students, enabling them to apply knowledge and skills professionally in machine component and mechanism design.

The methodological component of the model is based on theories and methodologies of teaching general technical disciplines, higher professional education principles, and the concept of integrating all components of a holistic specialist training system. The content component encompasses fundamental laws, concepts, and scientific-technical theories studied in general technical disciplines [12-13]. It is professionally oriented toward solving engineering problems and considers continuity, succession, unity, and complementarity between courses. The learning process integrates the core “Mechanics” course, the accompanying OIT and P courses, academic competitions, and scientific research activities. This integration follows general and specific didactic principles, along with criteria for selecting educational material. The learning content directly contributes to achieving the stated objectives, while the objectives themselves define the structure of the learning content.

The objectives and content of the “Mechanics” course in technical universities are implemented within the process-technological component of the methodological system model, which includes teaching methods, learning formats, and educational tools. The principle of integrating fundamental, professionally oriented, and project-based knowledge and skills is realized through varied teaching methodologies. In addition to information-illustrative and reproductive methods, partially exploratory, problem-based, and research-based methods are also applied. Within this component, the core “Mechanics” course is regarded as a key academic discipline that shapes technology specialists.

Figure 2: Generalized Model of the Methodological System for the Formation of SIID and SIID technologies

“Mechanics” serves as the foundation of engineering knowledge, enabling students to develop essential general (key), subject-specific, and partially specialized competencies that define SIID. As an academic discipline, Mechanics is the science that studies the motion, equilibrium, and interaction of material bodies. As an applied science, it examines the fundamental principles of machines, mechanisms, and mechanical systems—covering their analysis, calculation, design, and development—thus fully aligning with the requirements of IID. Building upon natural sciences, Mechanics acts as both a carrier and a transmitter of fundamental knowledge into specialized disciplines. Our analysis of the course’s potential in shaping SIID focuses on three key components: the motivational-need component, the operational-activity component, and the higher mental functions component. The results demonstrate that studying mechanics contributes significantly to developing nearly all the competencies that define SIID.

An analysis of general professional knowledge structures has led to the formulation of specific requirements for the content of the Mechanics course, which support SIID formation. The content of the general technical discipline Mechanics is developed and implemented through the structural components of the methodolog-

ical system, including goal-oriented, content-based, procedural, and diagnostic elements. General technical training aimed at fostering SIID in students should integrate the core Mechanics course with accompanying subjects that facilitate SIID formation, such as Fundamentals of Engineering Creativity and Patent Studies, alongside independent work within Olympiads and scientific research. Academic disciplines in general technical training at technical universities should be considered as a unified system incorporating both content-based and procedural components. The core Mechanics course, along with other general technical and complementary subjects, should present scientific and technical knowledge holistically. The scientific component forms its invariant part, while the technical component constitutes its variable part. The variable part of the Mechanics course should align with students' professional and specialized training, ensuring that professionally oriented content is included in technical university curricula. General technical courses should be structured around fundamental physical and scientific-technical theories, ensuring the integrity of professional education. The educational-methodological complex (in both printed and digital formats) aimed at developing SIID should include not only traditional materials (such as syllabi and lecture notes) but also information-computer support systems. These systems should include electronic textbooks, applied software packages, and other digital tools that allow students to independently acquire knowledge, develop skills, and conduct self-assessments in the Mechanics course [14-15].

The diagnostic component of the methodological system model ensures regular monitoring and evaluation of SIID formation in technical university students, as well as their readiness for consciously choosing a future professional path in IID. This component is implemented through an information-computer support system (including electronic textbooks), multi-level tasks designed to assess students' preparedness for Olympiads, and a structured testing system to evaluate the formation of motivational, content-based, and procedural components of innovative activities.

The Engineering Creativity Immersion Model consists of two parts: Olympiad-based learning and technical creativity training. The first part includes stages such as participant preparation, competition performance, and performance analysis. It is implemented within the framework of the All-Russian student Olympiads and competitions (first to third rounds), as well as summer scientific student schools. The model incorporates a system of didactic and subject-specific didactic principles, including independence, fundamentality, knowledge activation, complementarity, advanced learning, complexity, analysis-synthesis, continuity, MPF, knowledge effectiveness, and full mastery, along with the previously mentioned teaching methods and approaches. The model is universal, mobile, and manageable: Universality is ensured by its applicability to any stage, level, and type (method) of learning. Mobility is provided by the flexibility to enter or exit the system at any of the stages and cycles. Manageability is ensured by the educator's ability to influence the learning process in a timely manner. This type of learning represents a modeling of quasi-professional IID. Thus, as a result of the conducted research, a concept for the methodological system of SIID formation in technical university students has been developed, along with its model, which includes: Teaching the general technical discipline "Mechanics", The course "Fundamentals of Engineering Creativity and Patent Studies", Training within the environment of Olympiads and scientific research.

The content of the main course "Mechanics" is implemented in all forms of educational activities, including lectures, practical sessions, laboratory work, and course design projects [18-19]. The professionally oriented content of the course is determined based on an analysis of the interdisciplinary connections between the main course "Mechanics" and specialized disciplines. Additionally, an analysis of curricula and academic discipline content allows for the establishment of connections between general technical, natural science, and specialized disciplines, ensuring the formation of students' innovative engineering activity competencies (SIIE) within all components of the methodological system.

A method for forming the working curriculum is considered, taking into account: Knowledge of natural scientific theories, which form the basis of analysis, synthesis, and design of mechanical systems with optimal operational characteristics; Fundamental principles of general technical disciplines and their application in professionally relevant tasks; Implementation of fundamental and applied topics of general technical disciplines in the form of algorithms, design calculations, models, and projects within various components of a unified methodological system.

In this regard, the working curriculum, in addition to traditional topics, includes additional issues related to solving professional tasks for future engineering and innovative activities. All educational material in the main course "Mechanics" is structured into complete module-blocks, after studying each of which an intermediate knowledge assessment is conducted through a specially developed system based on an individual and differentiated approach, within the framework of personality-oriented and problem-based learning. The formation of these modules follows key principles for selecting and organizing educational material: generalization of educational material; scientifically justified systematization of physical and technical phenomena; structuring of educational material based on a systematic approach; flexibility, continuity, responsiveness, and dynamism of

the knowledge assessment system; and the principle of awareness of the need to develop the ability for innovative engineering activity (SIIE) [20-21].

Figure 3: Model of Immersion in Engineering Creativity

For example, in the theory of mechanisms and machines, six such modules were identified: Structure of mechanisms, Kinematics of mechanisms, Transmission of rotational motion, Cam mechanisms, Kinetostatics of mechanisms, and Dynamics of machines. Each of these modules is based on a specific fundamental physical or physical-technical theory. The structured material, presented in a specific sequence, is studied during various types of classes to achieve the main goal—the formation of SIIE in students.

For the successful implementation of modular learning, an information and computer support system for the main course "Mechanics" has been developed, including: Methodological support for the learning subsystem (lecture notes, teaching materials for various types of lessons, guidelines for organizing independent work, and training in Olympiad and research environments); Educational complexes (textbooks, study guides); A system of assignments for practical classes (collections of problems, differentiated into three levels of difficulty, with example solutions); A system of assignments for laboratory classes (manuals for laboratory practice, lists of demonstration and laboratory equipment, including for research and professionally oriented work); A system of assignments for course design projects (manuals for course design, teaching materials for performing calculation and graphic work, practice-oriented tasks for course projects, application software packages for calculating and designing mechanical system elements); A system of electronic resources (electronic textbooks developed in accordance with the curriculum and officially registered as required); Teaching and methodological materials for continuous knowledge assessment (materials for continuous student knowledge assessment at various stages of learning in the main course "Mechanics", including current, interim, and final assessments).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The necessity of forming and developing students' innovative engineering activity competencies (SIIE) in technical universities is justified, driven by the demand for such specialists in modern high-tech innovative enterprises. It has been demonstrated that such specialists can be prepared by organizing the following types of innovative engineering activities (IEA): innovative engineering understanding (analysis), subjective research and experimental design (synthesis), and innovative executive activities (manufacturing). The concept of "innovative engineering activity" has been specified, and the concept of "ability for innovative engineering activity" has been introduced, defining its structure, which includes 13 competencies that determine these abilities. Three levels of SIIE development (low, medium, and high) and their corresponding criteria have been established.

It has been shown that: Currently, the general technical cycle of disciplines does not sufficiently rely on natural science and innovation-oriented disciplines. Students do not fully realize the purpose of studying general technical disciplines, particularly Mechanics, as the foundation for specialized disciplines and their future professional innovative activities. Students struggle to transform knowledge from natural sciences into general technical and specialized disciplines and effectively apply them in course design and thesis projects using innovative technologies. Despite the necessity of training specialists ready for IEA, most teachers continue to educate students using the traditional disciplinary-streaming system. The highest efficiency in developing SIIE in technical university students is achieved through courses such as Mechanics, Engineering and Information Technologies (OIT and P), training in Olympiad and research environments, as well as natural science disciplines (especially physics). The main pedagogical technologies for forming SIIE include structuring scientific and technical knowledge, innovative teaching methods, collaboration technologies, and other advanced educational strategies.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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